

Limited Simulator Aircraft Handling Qualities Evaluation of an Adaptive Controller

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Abstract—The paper details the application and handling qualities evaluation through computer-based simulation of an adaptive model reference controller acting on the longitudinal modes of a fighter-type aircraft. Whereas classical control designs depend largely on a priori knowledge of the system dynamics, adaptive control algorithms do not require the same degree of a priori sophistication, or alternately the same controller can be applied on a plant with varying dynamics such as experienced by an aircraft over a wide range of flight conditions. Although the applications of an adaptive controller are well understood, much of the existing research focuses on an adaptive controllers' ability to track a basic input (such as step, ramp, or sinusoid) over a range of time-varying plants. In this research the adaptive controller is evaluated through a series of pilot-in-the-loop tracking tasks utilizing the boundary avoidance tracking technique designed to highlight potential control difficulties which may lead to pilot-in-the-loop oscillations, task abandonment or loss of control. The results presented will serve as a precursor to flight tests of adaptive controllers on-board next generation fighter aircraft.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Adaptive control for control problems is a promising endeavor. The advantages of adaptive methods for flight control are numerous. Adaptive methods are in many cases simpler to implement and program over a wide range of flight regimes with much less gain scheduling required. Another advantage of many types of adaptive methods is the limited requirement for a priori knowledge of the system dynamics to implement the algorithms. This advantage has a corresponding benefit in reducing implementation cost due to the decreased need for expensive wind tunnel testing and computational fluid dynamics to predict aircraft stability derivatives. Adaptive methods may also prove more flexible for handling unknown conditions such as battle damage or subsystem failures thus increasing aircraft safety margins.

Despite numerous advantages challenges remain in proving stability, optimality and the predictability of aircraft handling qualities. The focus of this paper was to assess the handling qualities of an aircraft model augmented by an adaptive controller. Before embarking on the test program a review of the existing literature was required.

2. BACKGROUND

The adaptive controller programmed for this aircraft handling qualities evaluation was based primarily on the work of Kaufman, Barkana, and Sobel[1]. This type of direct model reference adaptive controller (direct MRAC) has been shown repeatedly to perform on aircraft flight control problems. Sobel demonstrated the direct MRAC algorithm could stabilize the

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short period mode of a linear time-varying transport aircraft plant model [2] and also effectively applied a similar method on the lateral axis of model of a fighter aircraft [3]. Belkharraz and Sobel showed the direct MRAC's ability to control a multiple input, multiple output linear plant in response to step inputs [4], [5], [6].

Handling qualities testing of adaptive controllers for fighter aircraft has not been extensively reported in the literature. A Cooper-Harper evaluation of an L1 Adaptive controller was completed by Cotting et al in 2008 [7]. The testing showed an L1 Adaptive controller could be implemented in a longitudinal simulator model with resulting in qualitative favorable ratings.

For this paper the longitudinal dynamics of an aircraft simulation were augmented using the direct MRAC technique. The handling qualities evaluation conducted used the Boundary Avoidance Tracking (BAT) workload buildup flight test technique to track a reference pitch signal. The goal of the testing was to quantitatively assess the adaptive controller performance when applied to a pair of F-4C longitudinal dynamic cases. The augmented system was compared to the baseline reference model it was designed to emulate, the open loop F-4C models, and another model purposefully constructed with known poor handling qualities. The algorithm would be deemed successful if it performed indistinguishably from the reference model in comparison with the open loop F-4C models and known poor handling model.

3. MODELING AND SIMULATION

Aircraft Modeling

The aircraft models used as the baseline airframe response were based on the linear longitudinal models presented by Yechout et al[8]. The linear state space model may be written as

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u} \quad (1)$$

where the single input was elevator deflection δ_e in the input vector $\mathbf{u} = \delta_e$ and the states u longitudinal velocity, α angle of attack, q pitch rate and θ pitch angle were placed in the state vector

$$\mathbf{x} = \begin{Bmatrix} u \\ \alpha \\ q \\ \theta \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

The coefficient matrices A and B may be found in the Appendix as equations A-1 and equation A-2.

The baseline aircraft was the F-4C at flight conditions of pressure altitude equal to 35000 feet and Mach equal to 0.6. A notional relaxed stability aircraft was created by setting the longitudinal stability derivative M_α equal to zero.

The emphasis of this experiment was on the handling qualities of the longitudinal modes. Generally the phugoid is ignored for these cases. To stabilize and bound the phugoid, a simple proportional gain feedback loop was programmed to act on the change in airspeed. No other efforts to monitor or control the phugoid mode were required or attempted.

Adaptive Control Algorithm

An Adaptive Model Reference Controller was developed using the methods presented by Kaufman et al[1]. A system overview is seen in Figure 1.

The adaptive controller used pitch rate error, model states, and pilot longitudinal stick inputs to create a command signal. Briefly, the adaptive algorithm consists of a pitch rate model given as

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_m = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_m + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}_m \quad (3)$$

$$y_m = \mathbf{C}_m\mathbf{x}_m. \quad (4)$$

For the pitch rate control system, a reference pitch rate control model where $y_m \equiv q_m$. The model pitch rate q_m was created to emulate a level one aircraft based on MIL-STD-1797A (the relevant information may be found in Yechout [8]). The second order pitch rate model used was written in terms of damping ratio ζ and natural frequency ω_n given a pitch (elevator) stick input $u_m = \delta_{es}(t)$

$$q_m'' + 2\zeta\omega_n q_m' + \omega_n^2 q_m = \omega_n^2 \delta_{es}. \quad (5)$$

The values for ζ and ω_n for the level 1 reference model are provided in Table 1. A level 3 pitch rate model was con-

Table 1. Linear second order dynamics for pitch response (short period).

Linear system	ω_n (Hz)	ζ
Level 1	0.80	1.00
Level 3	0.80	0.15
F-4C M=0.6, 350000	0.23	0.26
F-4C M=0.6, 350000 $M_\alpha = 0$	0.09	1.00

structed for use in the experiment (as described in Section 3) and is also shown in the table. Finally, the F-4C short period plant dynamics are presented for comparison. In the case of the relaxed stability F-4C ($M_\alpha = 0$) there is also a slow unstable pole at 0.01 Hz. Both F-4C linear models in Table 1 were considered level 3 aircraft for the purposes of this experiment. In the experiment the level 1 models would be used as an open loop plant model and as a reference model. The other three models would be used as plant models only. The three open loop plants would be flown in open loop and closed loop

Figure 2. Control Algorithm.

Figure 3. Control Algorithm for Model States.

to quantitatively evaluate pilot performance for aircraft handling qualities and was described most recently by Gray in 2008 [9]. In this work the BAT theory was briefly summarized using a bicycle analogy.

The analogy of riding a bicycle across a beam has been a popular way to teach the concept of “gain” by graphically illustrating how the difficulty of the task changes the rider’s inputs. Imagine the task of riding a bicycle down a straight line painted in the middle of a parking lot; this illustrates the low-gain rider. If you take that path and elevate it to a deadly height (i.e. a bridge without rails) then make the path narrower and narrower, the rider will clearly increase his effort to stay on the painted line; an increase in gain. If the path is narrow enough, the rider’s gain becomes so high that he can no longer remain stable and oscillates off the narrow beam.

Traditional handling qualities analysis assumes that the risk of falling off the narrow beam increases the rider’s gain, perhaps to the point of triggering a pilot-induced oscillation (PIO). BAT theory states that the rider actually controls in relation to the edges. As the rider approaches an edge he is said

to engage in boundary avoidance tracking, where the boundary to be avoided is the edge of the beam. A singular instance of BAT at one edge can drive the rider into the other edge where the process repeats until the bicycle and rider tumble into the abyss.

To evaluate the different open loop and adaptively controlled longitudinal models, a time varying longitudinal desired pitch angle ($\theta_d(t)$) was described by the equation:

$$\theta_d(t) = \sin 0.25\pi t + \cos 0.2\pi t - \cos 0.1\pi t + \cos 0.04\pi t^2. \quad (12)$$

The command repeated itself every 20 seconds and was continuous at the reset point. The repeating signal may be seen in Figure 4. Pilots were instructed to track the signal within the

Figure 4. Desired pitch angle for Boundary Avoidance Tracking task.

confines of a time varying boundary initially set at $\pm 40^\circ$ centered on the command signal (that is it was initially equal to $\theta_d(t) \pm 40^\circ$). When the command signal reset every 20 seconds the boundary collapsed by 75% of the previous value. The experiment terminated when the pilot could no longer maintain the measured output pitch angle within the upper and lower boundaries.

To track the command signal the pilot was presented with the display shown in Figure 5. On the left hand side of the tape display a needle representing $\theta_d(t)$ pointed at the desired pitch angle. The upper and lower boundary were depicted by horizontal lines offset from the desired pitch angle needle. The system pitch angle measured output was indicated by a needle on the right side of the tape display. When the task was conducted, the right hand needle would move up and down the tape indicating measured pitch angle, while the left hand needle would move according to $\theta_d(t)$ with a boundary lines remaining a set offset from the desired angle. When the measured pitch output could no longer be maintained within the boundaries the experiment would end. The time value when this occurred was defined as T_f .

Figure 5. Workload task pitch angle tracking display.

The subjects used in this study were USAF Test Pilot School instructor test pilots. The pilots were from various flight backgrounds with no less than 2000 hours of flight experience. The pilots were trained in recognizing different flight models and characteristics and could be expected to perform maximum compensation necessary to obtain results. Therefore the experiments designed were necessarily challenging—the pilots were never asked not to perform at their highest capability.

The goal of the experiment was to determine if the adaptively controlled plant using a level 1 reference model would be distinguishable from a baseline open loop level 1 model and a level 3 model when using the BAT workload buildup flight test technique.

4. TEST CONDUCT, RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Seven trials were conducted where seven pilots performed the boundary tracking task. The pilots each “flew” the simulator in the configurations shown in Table 2. In the table each trial was characterized by a plant model (either a level 1 or 3 pitch rate model or an F-4C linear model) and an Augmentation scheme (either open loop or adaptive level 1). The trials were organized into three categories: Level 1 Model, Level 3 Model and (Adaptive Level 1) Model Follower.

The test trials were conducted in the following order: Trial 1, followed by a random ordering of Trials 2-5, Trial 6 and Trial 7. As the pilots in the study were familiar with the BAT technique and by studies of this nature, it was the opinion of the test team that pilot learning and adaptation to the task would not significantly affect the results. All data on the Simulink

”bus” were recorded. The data were analyzed using two different methods, performance results and aggressiveness versus duty cycle plots.

The Adaptive Level 1 Model Follower was able to provide a system pitch rate to pilot commands which closely resembled the reference model pitch rate. Figure 6 depicts a typical pitch rate for the adaptively controlled system. The reference model pitch rate to an elevator command was generated in degrees per second. The difference between the reference model pitch rate and the achieved pitch rate was also calculated and plotted (this is the error signal, e , which is one of the inputs to the adaptive controller). The figure shows the error rate was small in comparison to the reference model pitch rate.

Figure 6. Model pitch rate and pitch rate error with Adaptive Level 1 Model Follower (typical results).

The next two figures, Figure 7 and Figure 8, were created to show typical data gathered for each trial. Figure 7 shows a typical result for the Adaptive Level 1 Model Follower. For this case the pitch angle changes were smooth and the pilot was able to avoid the boundaries for an extended period of nearly 100 seconds. Contrast Figure 7 with Figure 8. Figure 8 shows erratic pitch angle changes which were more oscillatory and of higher frequency than the desired pitch angle θ_d . This response was indicative of the test pilot’s difficulty avoiding the boundaries when controlling the intentionally difficult to handle Level 3 open loop model. The pilot also exceeded the boundary and ended the trial in a much shorter time. This concept of performance was explored as the first quantifiable metric applied to the results of the experiment.

Performance

The first test result derived from the test data was performance. The overall performance was simply the length of time a specific configuration could be controlled before a boundary excursion occurred, or as defined previously T_f . These results are shown in Figure 9. A simple method to analyze the performance results was to compare the median values obtained by the pilots for the three trials. The Level

Table 2. Key to trials.

Trial	Plant Model	Augmentation	Analysis Data Group
1	Level 1	none (open loop)	Level 1 Model
2	F-4 35000 ft 0.6M	none (open loop)	Level 3 Model
3	F-4 35000 ft 0.6M	Adaptive Level 1	Model Follower
4	F-4 35000 ft 0.6M $M_\alpha = 0$	Adaptive Level 1	Model Follower
5	F-4 35000 ft 0.6M $M_\alpha = 0$	none (open loop)	Level 3 Model
6	Level 1 (repeat of trial 1)	none (open loop)	Level 1 Model
7	Level 3	none (open loop)	Level 3 Model

Figure 7. Results for BAT task with Adaptive Level 1 Model Follower (pilot 3, trial 3).

Figure 8. Results for BAT task with Level 3 model (pilot 3, trial 7).

Figure 9. Performance.

1 Model trials resulted in median performance values of 96.9 and 95.6 seconds, the Level 3 Model trials resulted in median values of 60.0, 40.0 and 53.0 seconds and the Adaptive Level 1 Model Follower median values were 101.7 and 97.4 seconds. Numerical test results for all trials and pilots are provided in Appendix Table A-2. Given the performance difference of over 30 seconds from the highest Level 3 median and the lowest Level 1 (open loop or adaptive model following) clearly indicates the adaptive control system was operating on par with the Level 1 Model baseline and superior to the Level 3 Model baseline. The small performance advantage the Adaptive Level 1 Model Follower maintained over the Level 1 Model baseline was not considered to be statistically significant and no performance advantage should be claimed.

Analyzing the results resulted in an additional observation regarding the use of the BAT technique. The boundaries collapsed instantaneously at intervals of 20 seconds. A review of the data indicated 4 of the 7 pilots performance data happened at a collapsing boundary time interval. Qualitatively pilots indicated the boundary collapse surprised them. Future BAT exercises should limit boundary collapse rate with a filter and the time constant should allow for a pilot normal pilot reaction time of 2-3 seconds. Other methods such as a time or

audible device could be explored but it is the opinion of the test team simply slowing the rate of collapsing boundaries would be sufficient.

Using performance as a metric the direct-MRAC control scheme was similar to an open loop system with the reference model dynamics. The next analysis measure was to plot aggressiveness versus duty cycle.

Aggressiveness versus Duty Cycle

The second measure of performance was the comparison of the cross plot of aggressiveness versus duty cycle. An explanation of the terms aggressiveness and duty cycle as they pertain to the BAT technique is warranted.

Aggressiveness was a measure of available control power used by the pilot. For this experiment where pilot stick deflections were previously defined as $\delta_{es}(t)$, aggressiveness, A_G , was defined as

$$A_G = 100\% \times \frac{1}{T_f} \int_0^{T_f} \left(\frac{|\delta_{es}(t)|}{\max \delta_{es}} \right) dt \quad (13)$$

In the above equation $\max \delta_{es}$ represents the maximum allowable stick travel. To explain this term a pilot who held full aft or forward stick for the entire duration would have an aggressiveness equal to 100%. Similarly a pilot who controlled stop to stop without pause in between switching sense would also have aggressiveness equal to 100%. A pilot who used less of the available control authority would have a lower overall percentage. Large control movements usually indicate either complete confidence in the system or a desperate measure to maintain system performance for an untrained pilots. In general, USAF test pilots were trained to avoid abnormally large control inputs at the brink of control.

This definition of aggressiveness differs slightly from the definition first proposed by Gray[9] which defined aggressiveness as "root-mean squared per-second average of the inceptor measurand (position or force) rate of change." However it is the opinion of the research team for this experiment the refined definition was adequate measure of available control power used by the pilot. After characterizing aggressiveness, pilot behavior was characterized by another metric termed duty cycle.

Duty Cycle was the term used to characterize pilot in-the-loop actions. In simple terms it was the percentage of time the pilot was moving the stick as opposed to holding it at a constant value. It is hypothesized pilot workload increases with increased duty cycle although task abandonment would be characterized by 0% duty cycle. For the purposes of this

experiment duty cycle, $D.C.$ was mathematically defined as

$$D.C. = 100\% \times \frac{1}{T_f} \int_0^{T_f} F(t) dt$$

where

$$F(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \left| \frac{d}{dt} \delta_{es}(t) \right| > 0 \\ 0, & \left| \frac{d}{dt} \delta_{es}(t) \right| = 0 \end{cases} \quad t \in [0, T_f]. \quad (14)$$

For a digital system it was not practical to calculate the derivative of the pilot elevator stick input—the digital output of the stick potentiometer was limited to approximately 80 discrete values. The derivative in Equation 14 was simply approximated as a non-zero value when the output of the pitch stick differed from its corresponding value in the previous 100 milliseconds (derivative nonzero at time t_k when $\delta_{es}(t_k) \neq \delta_{es}(t_k - .1)$).

Figure 10 displays the test results for aggressiveness versus duty cycle. Two general observations may be made. It is

Figure 10. Pilot workload: Aggressiveness versus duty cycle.

worth recalling that all data recorded were from pilots accomplishing identical pitch tracking tasks except for the dynamic model or algorithm evaluated. First, the Adaptive Level 1 Model Follower and the Level 1 Model were characterized by more aggressive inputs by the pilot than the Level 3 Model experiments. It was the opinion of the test team greater aggressiveness was the result of greater confidence in the system response. The second observation was duty cycle measured for the 3 categories of pitch BAT simulations were roughly equivalent. From these two general observations it was concluded the Adaptive Level 1 Model Follower was indistinguishable from the baseline Level 1 Model in terms of pilot aggressiveness and duty cycle but only clearly distinguishable from an ill-handling Level 3 model based on the aggressiveness metric.

Areas for Future Research

Future research based on the results of this study lie in two distinct arenas. The first arena is further application and development of the adaptive control algorithms, while the second arena lies in refinement of the boundary area tracking technique.

The adaptive control algorithm for this study, Kaufman's direct model reference adaptive controller, yielded encouraging results but it is noted the algorithm was applied in an admittedly benign environment. The ultimate goal is to apply the algorithm in a flight experiment on a fighter aircraft such as the USAF TPS F-16 VISTA, but in order to do so a build-up in mathematically rigorous simulation and theoretical development is required. Aircraft longitudinal model dynamics were linear, single-input/single-output and de-coupled from lateral dynamics. The adaptive control algorithm may handle multiple-input/multiple-output square systems—a lateral-directional application is a logical next step. Computer simulations to include handling qualities evaluations with a non-linear model in a high-fidelity aircraft simulator should also be attempted where actuator and aircraft structural dynamics are also represented. An examination of the effects on system dynamics in general (especially stability) and aircraft handling qualities in particular of proportional versus integral adaptive gains as well as trade studies in weighting of input, state and error adaptive gains should also be conducted. Handling qualities evaluation test cases should be chosen which are traditionally difficult for adaptive algorithms—it is envisioned fast changing, unstable and non-linear dynamics with tight error tolerances would be interesting to study. A side-by-side comparison with learning adaptive algorithms (such as neural networks) or other adaptive schemes (such as fuzzy logic) may also be explored for handling qualities differences.

Where the path forward for developing the adaptive algorithms appears relatively straightforward, further refinement of the boundary area tracking workload buildup flight test technique requires some imagination. At its core the quantitative techniques for assessing an aircraft's handling qualities were successful in demonstrating the performance of the adaptive control algorithm versus baseline models, but it was not demonstrated (nor claimed) that the BAT technique was unique in its ability to deliver the data to arrive at this conclusion. A fundamental challenge of the BAT technique was the task dependence of its metrics of performance, duty cycle and aggressiveness. For the BAT technique to gain more universal acceptance attempts should be made to normalize the key metrics so that *different* tracking tasks may be directly compared. Once so defined, it may one day take a place with specifications such as allowable time delay, natural frequency and damping ratio.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The direct adaptive control algorithm was successfully implemented on a longitudinal linear aircraft model based on

the F-4C airframe dynamics for both a stable model and a notional model with relaxed static stability. A desired pitch rate command model was developed and the adaptive algorithm was used to augment the F-4C airframe models. Using the Boundary Avoidance Tracking test, seven test pilots performed a simulator-based pitch rate tracking exercise. Based on Performance and Aggressiveness quantitative metrics the adaptive algorithm augmented system performed similar to the reference model it was set to emulate while the bare airframe and control group models chosen for their poor handling qualities were readily identified.

Based on the results presented, further development of the direct adaptive control algorithm with the goal of conducting pilot-in-the-loop evaluations using high fidelity simulation and in-flight test techniques should continue. The results also highlight the need to refine and normalize results derived from the application of the Boundary Avoidance Tracking workload buildup flight test technique to broaden its applicability.

APPENDIX

The linear state space models require coefficient matrices A and B . The coefficient matrices were

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} X_u & X_\alpha & 0 & -g \cos \theta_1 \\ \alpha_{SF} Z_U / U_1 & \alpha_{SF} Z_\alpha / U_1 & \alpha_{SF} (1 + Z_q / U_1) & \alpha_{SF} (-g \sin \theta_1 / U_1) \\ M_U + M_{\dot{\alpha}} \alpha_{SF} Z_U / U_1 & M_\alpha + M_{\dot{\alpha}} \alpha_{SF} Z_\alpha / U_1 & M_q + M_{\dot{\alpha}} \alpha_{SF} (1 + Z_q / U_1) & M_{\dot{\alpha}} \alpha_{SF} (-g \sin \theta_1 / U_1) \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (A-1)$$

and

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} X_{de} \\ \alpha_{SF} Z_{de} / U_1 \\ M_{de} + M_{\dot{\alpha}} \alpha_{SF} Z_{de} / U_1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (A-2)$$

The longitudinal dimensional derivatives values for the F-4C at flight conditions of 35000 feet, $M=0.6$ were reported by Yechout [8] and repeated in Table A-1.

Table A-1. F-4C Longitudinal Dimensional Derivatives.

Variable	Value
M	0.6
U_1 (fps)	584
α_{SF} (deg)	9.4
X_u	-0.0176
X_α	-24.25
Z_u	-0.116
Z_α	-162.2
Z_q	0
M_u	-0.0001
M_α	-1.927
$M_{\dot{\alpha}}$	-0.144
M_q	-0.307
X_{de}	-0.01
Z_{de}	-20.98
M_{de}	-4.90

Three tables (Tables A-2, A-3 and A-4) summarize the test results.

Table A-2. Test Results: Performance (seconds)

Pilot	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Trial 6	Trial 7
1	97.2100	60.0110	72.0800	95.6400	40.0000	77.4800	37.6850
2	97.1800	80.0000	112.0000	97.4100	39.9210	97.3100	72.2400
3	57.5800	60.0000	97.0100	97.1900	38.1840	111.8700	53.0400
4	77.1800	59.9600	118.5100	117.0100	60.0000	80.0100	72.3000
5	112.3800	80.0000	118.3690	111.8800	60.0000	89.9900	52.6400
6	96.9200	53.4880	101.7670	94.2900	77.2700	95.6800	53.0200
7	76.9500	58.9910	97.0400	112.8000	40.0000	97.1100	24.3430
mean	87.9143	64.6357	102.3966	103.7457	50.7679	92.7786	52.1811
median	96.9200	60.0000	101.7670	97.4100	40.0000	95.6800	53.0200

Table A-3. Test Results: Aggressiveness

Pilot	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Trial 6	Trial 7
1	0.3543	0.1168	0.2813	0.3481	0.1812	0.3074	0.1961
2	0.3519	0.1471	0.3168	0.3299	0.2286	0.3432	0.2353
3	0.2936	0.1387	0.3248	0.3187	0.1759	0.3204	0.1812
4	0.3227	0.1663	0.3797	0.3387	0.2301	0.3682	0.1987
5	0.3832	0.1367	0.3769	0.3463	0.2086	0.3257	0.1850
6	0.4051	0.1307	0.3850	0.3663	0.1293	0.3962	0.1650
7	0.3554	0.1463	0.3611	0.3715	0.2359	0.3569	0.2102
mean	0.3523	0.1404	0.3465	0.3456	0.1985	0.3454	0.1959
median	0.3543	0.1387	0.3611	0.3463	0.2086	0.3432	0.1961

Table A-4. Test Results: Duty Cycle

Pilot	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Trial 6	Trial 7
1	0.7945	0.7090	0.7415	0.7385	0.7080	0.7367	0.6902
2	0.8235	0.8384	0.8108	0.8010	0.8776	0.8025	0.8420
3	0.6705	0.7170	0.6660	0.7129	0.6609	0.7513	0.5882
4	0.7467	0.6420	0.7072	0.7275	0.7447	0.6296	0.7277
5	0.8276	0.7551	0.7352	0.7326	0.7376	0.7539	0.8315
6	0.7888	0.6882	0.7468	0.7562	0.7107	0.7056	0.8232
7	0.7308	0.7368	0.7356	0.8142	0.7420	0.7887	0.5127
mean	0.7689	0.7266	0.7347	0.7547	0.7402	0.7383	0.7165
median	0.7888	0.7170	0.7356	0.7385	0.7376	0.7513	0.7277

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BIOGRAPHY

Michael Shepherd is the Director, Technical Support Division at the United States Air Force Test Pilot School. Lieutenant Colonel Shepherd's research interests include structural dynamics of aerospace structures and aircraft flight control. Lt Col Shepherd obtained a B.S. in engineering mechanics from the USAF Academy in 1990, and an M.S. in aeronautical and astronautical engineering from the University of Washington in 1991, and a Ph.D. from the Air Force Institute of Technology in 2006. He is a master navigator with over 3000 flight hours in operational and developmental test aircraft, a graduate of the USAF Test Pilot School and a member of AIAA.

Adam MacDonald received the B.S.E.E. degree in electrical engineering from the University of Massachusetts in 1988 and M.S.E.E. and Ph.D degrees in electrical engineering from the Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT) in 1999 and 2006 respectively. He gained his Air Force commission in 1988 and flew the F-15C as an operational fighter pilot and as an experimental test pilot. A graduate of the Air Force Test Pilot School, Lieutenant Colonel MacDonald has flown over 30 different aircraft and has accumulated over 2000 flight hours in fighter-type aircraft. He has worked on diverse developmental test programs such as Laser Radar, AIM-9X, Combat-ID, Fighter Data-Link, and avionics modernization for the T-38C. He is currently assigned as Director of Education and Instructor Test Pilot at the US Air Force Test Pilot School, Edwards Air Force Base, California, and is an Adjunct Professor at AFIT.

William Gray is the Chief Test Pilot for the USAF Test Pilot School at Edwards AFB, CA. He earned his B.S. at the US Air Force Academy (physics) and his M.S. in mechanical engineering at California State University, Fresno. An associate fellow of the Society of Experimental Test Pilots and Member of AIAA, Mr. Gray is currently conducting research on aircraft handling qualities evaluation, developing a reconfigurable variable stability flying qualities simulator and instructing student test pilots in the T-38, F-16, and NF-16D VISTA aircraft. A graduate of the USAF Test Pilot School, Mr. Gray has accumulated over 4500 hours in 80 diverse aircraft types.

Richard Cobb is an Assistant Professor of Aerospace Engineering in the Department of Aeronautical and Astronautical Engineering, Air Force Institute of Technology, WPAFB, Ohio. His research focuses on dynamics and control of large structures for space-based remote sensing and structural health monitoring for aerospace applications. Dr. Cobb received his B.S. in aerospace engineering from the Pennsylvania State University in 1988, an M.S. in astronautical engineering from the Air Force Institute of Technology in 1992, and a Ph.D. from the Air Force Institute of Technology in 1996. Dr. Cobb is an associate fellow of AIAA.